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A STUDY ON SERVICE QUALITY AND CUSTOMER LOYALTY TOWARDS CITY UNION BANK – WITH SPECIAL REFERENCE TO TIRUNELVELI DISTRICT

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Abstract: The banking industry, being very cutthroat, not only focuses on providing wide product lines to create competitive advantages but also emphasizes the importance of its services, particularly in maintaining service quality. Today's Customers are deeply concerned about having a high-quality experience of Banking. Excellent customer service, differentiated customer experience, and competitive propositions are the foundation of customer loyalty. Banks have a huge amount of data on customer spending habits so they are perfectly positioned to offer reward programs that feel unique to each customer. The primary purpose of the study is to diagnose accurately the service shortfall in City Union bank in Tirunelveli District. To complete the analysis, a well-structured questionnaire is distributed to 120 and collected back 113 and among them, 5 were incomplete so my sample size is 108. In the study on service quality of City Union bank in Tirunelveli District, the convenient sampling method has to be taken. It is concluded that the survival and growth of the bank does not depend on the size of the funds rather it depends on its ability to provide qualitative service to its customer on a sustained basis.

Keywords: Service Quality, Customer Loyalty, City Union Bank

INTRODUCTION

The banking industry, being very competitive, not only focuses on providing wide product lines to create competitive advantages but also emphasizes the importance of its services, particularly in maintaining service quality. Today's Customers are deeply concerned about having a high-quality experience of Banking. They expect an amiable atmosphere and entertainment and prefer banks with a personality rather than those perceived as offering a commodity. Quality of service is becoming an increasingly important differentiator between competing businesses in the Banking sector. In a fiercely competitive marketplace, characterized by similarly priced, lookalike product offerings from a variety of Financial Institutions, clear winners will be the ones that provide excellent service quality. Delivering quality to customers is paramount to a company's well-being because it results in more new customers, more business with existing customers, fewer lost customers, more protection

from price competition, and fewer mistakes requiring the company to redo its goods/services (Albrecht and Zemke 1985). The task of Banks is to balance customer expectation and perception and to close any gaps. Excellent customer service, differentiated customer experience, and competitive propositions are the foundation of customer loyalty. Banks have a huge amount of data on customer spending habits so they are perfectly positioned to offer reward programs that feel unique to each customer. The primary purpose of the study is to diagnose accurately the service shortfall in City Union bank in Tirunelveli Municipal Corporation. The main objective of the study is to find out the service quality and customer loyalty towards City Union bank in Tirunelveli District.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The following are the main objectives of the study

1. To find out the perception of customers towards the service quality of City Union bank in Tirunelveli Municipal Corporation.
2. To find out the customers Loyalty towards the City Union bank in Tirunelveli Municipal Corporation.
3. To suggest the City Union banks for improving their service quality.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Dr. Ali Sajid, Asad Ilyas et al., (2013) Our results show that the banking institutions are exceeding customer expectations in three dimensions i.e. “Tangibles”, “Reliability” and “Responsiveness” and lacking other two dimensions “Assurance” and “Empathy”. The main reason behind this satisfaction is a high level of competition among the banks in Pakistan and another reason might be the strong regulatory framework of banks in Pakistan. Although the service quality gap is very low on both sides so the banks should take serious steps to cater to the dissatisfaction among their customers.

Balwinder Singh and Ruchika Soni (2015) study is a genuine attempt to understudy the construct of customer satisfaction and the factor affecting customer satisfaction in the urban co-operative banking sector in the states of Punjab, Haryana, and Himachal Pradesh through a qualitative approach. The very widely representative profile of respondents helps us to reply and appropriately weigh the above outcomes.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is the systematic way to solve the research problem. It gives an idea about the various steps systematically adopted by the research with objectives to a study on service quality of City Union bank in Tirunelveli Municipal Corporation.

- **PRIMARY DATA**

Primary data are those data that are collected for the first time by the investigation for our use. It will be an original character for our study use questionnaire as primary data. In the study, the primary data was collected from the samples by using questionnaires and personal interviews.

- **SECONDARY DATA**

Secondary data are those data that are already collect and analyzed by someone for some purpose and later for some purpose and the same data used for a different purpose. The data were taken from websites, magazines, and journals.

- **SAMPLE SIZE**

To complete the analysis, a well-structured questionnaire is distributed to 120 and collected back 113 and among them, 5 were incomplete so my sample size is 108.

- **RESEARCH DESIGN**

A research design is considered as the frame or plan for a study that guided as well as helps the data collection and analysis of data. Research design is a detailed blueprint used to guide the research study towards its objectives.

- **SAMPLING TECHNIQUES**

In the study on service quality of City Union bank in Tirunelveli Municipal Corporation, the convenient sampling method has to be taken. Samples are selected at the convenience of the researcher.

- **STATISTICAL TOOLS**

The statistical tools help us to evaluate the problems under the study in a judicial manner. While analyzing the primary data, statistical tools such as percentage analysis, Garrett ranking, weighted average method, chi-square, and t-test techniques are used in this study.

HYPOTHESES

The following hypothesis made for analysis

- 1) There is no association between monthly family income and monthly average savings in City Union bank.
- 2) There is no association between Gender and customer loyalty in City Union bank.

DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE

- The majority (51.85 percent) of the respondents are male.
- The majority (60.19 percent) of the respondents are the married.
- The majority (26.85 percent) of the respondents are private employees.
- The majority (40.74 percent) of the respondents are getting a monthly family income of Rs. 20,001-30,000.
- The majority (38.89 percent) of the respondents have a monthly saving of Rs 5,000.
- The majority (38.89 percent) of the respondents save Rs.2,001-4,000, particularly in City Union Bank

Table 1: Factors Motivate to Prefer City Union Banking Services

Sl. No.	Factors	Weighted Garrett Score	Weighted Average Garrett Score	Rank
1	Fast transaction	6458	59.80	I
2	Safe transaction	5751	53.25	VI
3	Bank service charges	5875	54.40	IV
4	Social media banking	5844	54.11	V
5	Staff behaviour	5063	46.88	VIII
6	Existence of loan facility	5042	46.69	IX
7	Reasonable interest rate	4933	45.68	X
8	Accuracy	5281	48.90	VII
9	ATM facility	6360	58.89	III
10	Online saving account opening	6428	59.52	II

Source: Primary data

The above table expresses the factors that motivate them to prefer City Union bank services. The majority of the respondents feel that they are motivated by the Fast transaction followed by Online saving account opening and excellent ATM facility provided by City Union Bank.

Table 2: Customer Loyalty

Sl. No.	Factors	HS	S	M	DS	HDS	Total	Average Score	Rank
1	I am satisfied with new innovations and creativity made by CUB	49 (245)	32 (128)	18 (54)	5 (10)	4 (4)	441	88.2	I
2	I will do more business with CUB	23 (115)	42 (168)	33 (99)	7 (14)	3 (3)	399	79.8	II
3	I am extremely satisfied with financial services rendered by CUB	11 (55)	31 (124)	45 (135)	19 (38)	2 (2)	354	70.8	V
4	I consider myself to be loyal to CUB	26 (130)	32 (128)	37 (111)	8 (16)	5 (5)	390	78	III
5	CUB does good job of satisfying my needs.	24 (120)	26 (104)	44 (132)	8 (16)	6 (6)	378	75.6	IV

Source: Primary data

The above table represents that customer loyalty. The majority of the respondents feel that they are satisfied with innovations and creativity made by City Union bank followed by that they will do more business with City Union bank and they consider themselves to be loyal to City Union Bank.

Table 3: Positive Word of Mouth

Sl. No.	Factors	VH	H	M	L	VL	Total	Weighted Average	Rank
1	I say positive things about CUB to my friends, relatives associates etc.,	12 (60)	31 (124)	54 (162)	9 (18)	2 (2)	366	73.2	V
2	I encourage friends and colleagues to do business with CUB	21 (105)	46 (184)	28 (84)	8 (16)	5 (5)	394	78.8	II
3	I always talk about good financial services offered CUB to others.	19 (95)	31 (124)	40 (120)	10 (20)	8 (8)	367	73.4	IV
4	I am proud to say to others that I'm CUB customer	30 (150)	34 (136)	28 (84)	14 (28)	2 (2)	400	80	I
5	I will recommend my friends, relatives, and associates etc., to open in an account and do business with CUB	28 (140)	30 (120)	34 (102)	10 (20)	6 (6)	388	77.6	III

Source: Primary data

The above table expresses the positive word of mouth of the customers. The majority of the respondents feel that they feel proud to say to others that I'm a City Union bank customer followed by that they encourage their friends and colleagues to do business with City Union bank and they will recommend their friends, relatives, associates, etc., to open in an account and do business with City Union bank.

Table 4: Suggestion to Improve the Service Quality of City Union Bank

S. No.	Particulars	Weighted Garrett Score	Weighted Average Score	Rank
1.	Minimize bank service charges	5566	51.54	III
2.	Fast service	5016	46.44	VI
3.	Friendly services	5440	50.37	IV
4.	Adequate infrastructure	4688	43.41	VII
5.	Vehicle parking facility	5049	46.75	V
6.	Efficient and empathetic front office staff	5865	54.31	I
7.	Transparency	5628	52.11	II

Source: Primary data

The above table expresses the suggestions provided by the respondents to improve the service quality of the City Union Bank. The majority of the respondents feel that there should be efficient and empathetic front office staff, followed by transparency and minimizing bank service charges.

HYPOTHESES

Ho1: There is no association between Monthly Family Income and Monthly Average Savings in City Union Bank

Particulars	Calculated Value	Table value at 5%	Df	H ₀ accepted/ rejected
Chi- square	92.68	26.30	16	Rejected

Source: Primary data

Since Table value 26.30 is less than the calculated value of 92.68 the null hypothesis is rejected. There is an association between monthly family income and monthly average savings in City Union bank.

Ho2: There is no association between Gender and Customer loyalty in City Union bank.

Particulars	Calculated Value	Table value at 5%	Df	H ₀ accepted/ rejected
Chi- square	1.81	9.49	4	Accepted

Source: Primary data

Since the Calculated value of 1.81 is less than Table value 9.49 the null hypothesis is accepted. Therefore there is no association between gender and customer loyalty.

SUGGESTION

- ❖ Every banker should act in course of customer satisfaction not to bank employee satisfaction.
- ❖ The respondent expects to open many ATM centers in Tirunelveli Municipal Corporation.
- ❖ The respondents expect to open more branches of City Union bank in Tirunelveli Municipal Corporation.
- ❖ To decrease the interest rate on loans in City Union bank.
- ❖ To improve the security while using digital banking in City Union bank

CONCLUSION

The survival and growth of a bank do not depend on its size of the bank and it also does not depend on the size of the funds rather it depends on its ability to provide qualitative service to its customer on a sustained basis. This study and analysis have been made of the service rendered by the City Union bank. The suggestion offered would enable the bank to strengthen its relationship with the existing customer and increase the number of new customers.

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